

RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	<i>Neutron test for the photosensors Of the Crilin calorimeter (NOCal)</i>
Project TA identifier	<i>TA04-46</i>
General application	<i>High Energy Physics</i>
Type of test	<i>TNID</i>
Group leader, Institute	<i>Gianantonio Pezzullo, Yale</i>
Dates of the experiment	<i>27-31/06/2022</i>
Facility	<i>FNG</i>
Amount of access granted	<i>80</i>

Objectives of the experiments

Preliminary simulation studies showed that the BIB energy profile along the electromagnetic calorimeter is notably different with respect to the typical interactions of interest. The BIB interaction in the calorimeter is concentrated in the first layers (closer to the interaction point), while the interactions of interest go deeper in the detector. The Crilin geometry allows setting of variable thresholds for an optimal rejection of the BIB-induced signal. The same simulation studies showed that the Crilin calorimeter is expected to achieve similar or better performance (in terms of reconstruction efficiency and resolution) compared to its major competitor, the W-Si sampling calorimeter. Moreover, Crilin may cost a factor of 10 less than W-Si calorimeter.

The expected operational conditions for Crilin at the Muon collider are particularly harsh, with an expected total neutron fluence that can get as high as 10^{14} n/cm², it is thus pivotal for the team to characterize the calorimeter active components (SiPMs and Cherenkov crystals) to measure the induced damage and design mitigation strategy accordingly.

Experiment test report

We tested the components of a reduced scale prototype of the Crilin calorimeter: two PbF₂ crystals and four HAMAMATSU S14160 SiPMs with 10 and 15 μm pixel-size. Figure 1 shows the neutron gun at the Frascati Neutron source Generator facility (FNG) together with the support used to hold the SiPMs during the test as well as the simulated map of the total fluence used to choose the position for testing the SiPMs.

The SiPM neutron damage was evaluated by measuring the leakage current as a function of the bias voltage (IV curve). This measurement is particularly important to understand the necessary changes we need to apply during the operations of these photosensors, like variations in the cooling temperature or readout thresholds.

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Figure 1: Irradiation setup: on the top-left panel the SiPMs sample, where the two SiPMs series are separated by 1 cm, on the top-right panel the FNG reactor with a zoom (red box) on the neutron gun and the sample. On the bottom panel the irradiation levels reached on the sample, the white squares correspond to the position of the SiPMs.

Figure 2: Dark current as a function of the over-voltage (with respect to the break-down voltage) at different temperatures for 15 μm (left) and 10 μm (right) pixel-size SiPMs after a neutron irradiation of 10¹⁴ n/cm².

The test apparatus consists of: (i) a source meter KEYTHELEY 6487, used to bias the photosensor and measure the drained current, (ii) a chiller to regulate the working temperature, (iii) a small nitrogen bottle to be fluxed in the (cooled) electronics region to avoid condensation, (iv) a black box to house the prototype with all the front-end electronics.

Figure 2 shows the dark current as a function of the over-voltage, measured with respect the breakdown voltage, at different operational temperatures eighty hours after the neutron irradiation. The same figure shows that for the 10 μm pixel- size case, cooling the SiPMs at -10°C allows to obtain a dark current below 2 mA at $\Delta V = 4\text{ V}$, which is a factor 5 smaller than the one observed in the 15 μm pixel-size SiPM.

The same I-V scans were used also to study how the breakdown varies as a function of the SiPM temperature. Figure 3 shows the dependence of the break- down voltage as a function of the temperature. A linear fit to the data points provides the breakdown voltage variation per unit of temperature; for the 15 μm SiPM case, we obtained $9.8\%/^\circ\text{C}$, while for the 10 μm one $7.3\%/^\circ\text{C}$.

It was important for us also to measure the induced damage in the PbF2 crystals. The PbF2 is a Cherenkov crystal, thus the neutron-induced damage was evaluated by focusing on the resulting deterioration in the optical transmittance. One of the crystals was tested without any kind of wrapping (in the following referred as the "naked" one), the other one was wrapped with a 100 μm thick Mylar foil. Figure 4 shows the comparison of the transmission spectra before and after the neutron irradiation. In the first cm of the crystals the total fluence was 10^{13} n/cm^2 , while in the fourth cm it was 4.98×10^{11} : a reduction of a factor ~ 20 in the fluence is observed at the two edges of the crystal.

Due to the technical time related to logistics and shipment of the crystals, transmittance measurements could only be performed 14 days after the irradiation. However, this delay has shown again the natural annealing properties of this crystals since no alteration in the transmittance spectrum has been observed.

Figure 3: Breakdown voltage as a function of temperature for the 15 μm (left) and 10 μm (right) pixel-size SiPMs after irradiation. A linear fit was overlaid.

Figure 4: Transmission spectra obtained after the irradiation at FNG with 14 MeV neutrons for a total fluence of 10^{13} n/cm² (orange line) compared with the results after the 16 hours optical bleaching (blue line) for the naked crystal (left) and for the crystal with Mylar wrapping (right).

Summary

The Crilin calorimeter is an R&D project for a novel electromagnetic calorimeter to be used in the Muon collider program. Simulation studies showed that its expected performance are comparable or even better than its competitor, the W-Si sampling calorimeter. A small prototype of the Crilin calorimeter is under construction at the LNF. The neutron test was fundamental to qualify and characterize the active components of the Crilin calorimeter: SiPMs and PbF2 Cherenkov crystals. A total flux of $10^{14(13)}$ n_{1MeVeq} /cm² was delivered to the SiPMs (crystals) to reproduce the expected working condition in the Muon collider environment. The results showed negligible effects in the optical transmittance of the PbF2 crystals, while for the SiPM case, we measured the effects on the increased leakage current at different working temperatures, which is pivotal to properly design the cooling system of the readout electronics in the future Crilin applications.

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	
Data for Thesis	X
Follow-up experiment at same facility	X
Follow-up experiment at another facility	
Other	

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

RADNEXT acknowledgment:

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